

Designing computational systems to support humanities and social sciences research

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Abstract

From the viewpoint of the humanities and social sciences, collaborations with computer scientists often fail to deliver. In my research group, we have tried to understand why this is, and what to do about it. In this talk, I will discuss three key elements that we have discovered:

Often, datasets in the humanities and social sciences are not neatly representative of the object of interest. Systems need to provide ways in which to evaluate and counter the biases, confounders and noise in the data. Often, there is also a large gap between what is in the data, and what would be of interest. This gap needs to be bridged using algorithms, but care must be given that a) what the algorithm produces actually matches the interest and b) that its application does not introduce bias of its own (also interestingly, algorithm performance metrics of interest here often differ from those generally used in NLP/computer science). On a process level, collaboration between researchers from different disciplines is hard due to discrepancies in expectations relating to all facets of research, from research questions through methodology to the publication of results. Projects and systems need to acknowledge this, and be designed to facilitate iterative movement in the right direction.

Bio

Eetu Mäkelä is an associate professor in Human Sciences–Computing Interaction at the University of Helsinki, and a docent (adjunct professor) in computer science at Aalto University. At the Helsinki Centre for Digital Humanities, he leads a research group that seeks to figure out the technological, processual and theoretical underpinnings of successful computational research in the humanities and social sciences.

Additionally, he serves as a technological director at the DARIAH-FI infrastructure for computational humanities and is one of three research programme directors in the datafication research initiative of the Helsinki Institute for Social Sciences and Humanities. For his work, he has obtained a total of 19 awards, including multiple best paper awards in conferences and journals, as well as multiple open data and open science awards. He also has a proven track record in creating systems fit for continued use by their audience.